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INCREASING DIVERSITY WITHIN SCIENTIFIC ORGANIZATIONS TO MEET THE CHALLENGES OF DIGITALIZATION

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Annotation: Current requirements for the creation of intelligent systems for the collection, analysis and use of scientific data require a combination of comparative analysis procedures and the process of monitoring the scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects effectiveness. An analytical study of the feasibility of a large-scale application of scientometric systems has been carried out, and the main problems of the widespread implementation of interdisciplinary research projects have been identified. As part of the study, a new scientific and methodological approach was proposed to solve the scientific problem of diversifying scientific research. Methods and tools have been developed for a comprehensive qualitative comparison and ranking of interdisciplinary research projects with known indicators of efficiency (utility).

Keywords: performance monitoring, intelligent systems, diversification, scientometrics, digital technologies

A systematic assessment of the scientific organizations performance indicators values in relation to each other provides the possibility of detecting certain signals of control charts [1, 2]. At the same time, the occurrence of a systematic trend in the placement of points on the control map is monitored, which indicates the presence of a trend in the average value of the scientific and technical process. The use of reference ranges of efficiency makes it possible to compare the level of scientific performance of scientific organizations that are at the same hierarchical level, which provides a solution to the question of whether management decisions are effective or not.

An intelligent system for evaluating the scientific organizations' effectiveness should ensure the implementation of the main monitoring functions and the ability to compare results with best practices in the implementation of interdisciplinary projects, as well as take into account the specifics of the research

object and facilitate the adoption of effective management decisions to improve scientific performance.

Digital innovations make it possible to implement measures to improve the efficiency of using the limited resources of scientific organizations [3, 4]. One of the most important tasks is to solve the problems of scientific research diversification. With the advent of scientometric systems, the use of various decision support methods in science is becoming increasingly relevant [5, 6]. In recent years, a large number of scientific and practical works have been published that highlight the issues of effective use of interdisciplinary research projects, including the implementation of digital technology systems [7, 8]. Almost all researchers and practitioners emphasize the important potential role of digitalization in scientific and technological development. Typical for the preparatory stage of digital production are the issues of determining the investment attractiveness of various options (alternatives) of modern innovative technologies or equipment for including the best of them in the innovation and investment projects of scientific organizations. In other words, the problem arises of choosing the best among interdisciplinary projects in terms of their scientific effectiveness.

The traditional approach in such situations is to compare and rank alternatives by only one performance indicator, which is considered the main one, all other indicators form limitations [9, 10]. However, it is obvious that the most economical and technically efficient investment requires a scientifically based approach that can comprehensively take into account the full set of performance indicators of compared interdisciplinary research projects. In this case, there are specific problems of a general nature, the solution of which is aimed at the developed methods of decision support.

The production efficiency of scientific organizations is characterized by many indicators. In particular, the main scientometric indicators are set by their maximum values or ranges of values. Purely qualitative information, for example, about the actuality or relevance of interdisciplinary research projects, can also be important in the choice. Among the indicators of the scientific organizations' effectiveness in the context of digitalization, such indicators as technical and technological, socio-economic, environmental are singled out. The performance indicators of scientific organizations can be numerical data given by a single number, fuzzy numerical interval or graphical data, as well as qualitative scientific characteristics.

The task is to comprehensively (multi-criteria) compare and rank alternatives for interdisciplinary projects of scientific organizations in terms of the totality of these indicators. To do this, it is possible to use various special methods adapted to consider situations of indicators' contradiction, when some alternatives are the best for some indicators, and the worst ones for others, and therefore the complex ranking of all alternatives is uncertain. This uncertainty is fundamental,

and in such situations additional information is needed. Most often, it comes down to providing a decision maker (DM) to each of the conflicting indicators of a certain relative weight (priority), reflecting its subjective advantages. However, in this task there is another problem related to the fact that the decision maker, as a rule, does not have narrow special knowledge on specific high-tech technologies of the digital economy and therefore does not have certain guidelines when choosing the best of them. On the other hand, the decision maker may have his own global vision of the problem, and also bears full responsibility for the final choice [11, 12]. To help decision makers make their own choices after consulting with experts, various, mostly interactive, qualitative decision support methods are used.

A significant choice of different decision support methods, their diversity is explained by the fact that each of them has its own advantages and disadvantages [13, 14]. It follows that the larger this number, the easier it is for each specific problem to choose the most adequate method [15, 16]. As part of the study, a new scientific and methodological approach was proposed to solve the scientific problem of diversifying scientific research. The developed methods and tools are of a general nature and can be used for a comprehensive qualitative comparison and ranking of interdisciplinary projects of scientific organizations with known indicators of efficiency (utility).

The mathematical model has a hierarchical structure and is based on a comprehensive assessment of scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects and the creation of competition between them by means of linear programming. The problem of linear programming is formalized. The parameters of the model are transformed depending on the performance indicators of the alternatives so that these parameters increase with the improvement of the indicators. Under such conditions, the effectiveness for each alternative will be taken into account the full set of its indicators and it will increase with the improvement of each indicator, so the scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects effectiveness can be considered a comprehensive qualitative assessment of the effectiveness of the alternative for all its indicators, and the components of the optimal plan ranked by their value are multifactorial ranking of alternatives in terms of efficiency.

Based on individual indicators of two types of alternatives of scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects, the maximum and minimum values of the indicator in the group of alternatives are calculated. The possibility of transformation is also implemented, if the indicator is fuzzy and has an expert assessment, then its private assessment is the principle of optimality. With the improvement of individual indicators of a certain alternative, the corresponding partial estimates of it increase. Further, all performance indicators are divided into main and secondary ones.

We obtain a two-criteria problem with two given complex criteria, in which the importance coefficients realize the influence of the main, and the

parameters – of the secondary indicators on the complex ranking of alternatives for scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects in terms of all indicators. If in each of the indicated two groups the indicators are approximately equivalent to each other, then we find complex assessments of alternatives for scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects as a product of the corresponding partial assessments. If at least in one group the indicators are not equivalent to each other, then we obtain the corresponding comprehensive assessment of interdisciplinary projects of scientific organizations in a hierarchical way.

The practical application of the model is as follows. From the considered group of alternatives for scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects, it is advisable to single out the Pareto set of only dominant alternatives with conflicting indicators, after which their complex ranking is determined by their efficiency ratings.

The decision maker searches for the optimal ranking option by gradually increasing the model parameters, visualizing the dependence of performance estimates and comparative analysis of scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects. It is possible to establish precisely the general properties of scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects only analytically.

It is proposed to number the alternatives of scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects of in descending order of efficiency coefficients. Then there is a parameter that shows how many times the sum of all upper limits exceeds the sum of all efficiency estimates.

The boundary conditions for the scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects implementation involve competitors with large efficiency coefficients, which are further enhanced by the dependence of the upper bounds on these coefficients. It can be shown that when the parameter value is slightly greater than one, the alternative with the lowest performance score gets the remainder of the distribution of scores among the best alternatives, and its performance score becomes smaller, while the scores of the best alternatives are still equal to their upper bounds. Therefore, as the values of the model parameters increase, the estimates of the best alternatives increase linearly, while the estimates of the worst alternatives decrease linearly. After that, the interdisciplinary project is out of competition and the dimension of the problem decreases. The alternative with the lowest value of the efficiency indicator becomes the new subordinate among the rest of the competitors. The estimate of this alternative at the initial point is maximum, and then it begins to decrease with increasing parameter values, and everything is repeated for this reduced set of alternatives. Finally, of all the competitors, only the first alternative with the highest efficiency rating remains. This shows that all alternatives, except for the first one, successively pass to the status of a subordinate alternative.

In the general case, the efficiency curves of scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects are broken lines, including a line of growth with a maximum at one point and a line of decrease. For each alternative of scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects, the efficiency curves do not intersect with each other, and they have intersection points only with descending lines. Therefore, for an arbitrary value of the parameters, the alternatives are divided into the best, subordinate and worst.

For the worst alternatives of scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects, the efficiency coefficient is equal to the number of the alternative, that is, its rank in terms of the value of the coefficient, and for the best it coincides with the rank of the alternative in terms of the value of its upper limit. Thus, at the value of the parameters is equal to one only when, for all alternatives of scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects, the impact of the coefficients of the main indicators and the parameters of the secondary indicators on the complex ranking is symmetrical, that is, the same. For parameter values greater than one, this applies only to the best alternatives for scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects, and with an increase in the value of the indicator, the proportion of alternatives appears and then gradually increases, the ranks of which are equal to their rank in terms of the efficiency coefficient and do not depend on secondary indicators. Finally, when the value of the parameters is greater than some boundary value, all alternatives become such. It follows that the model parameter determines the relative importance of the influence of the main indicators on the complex ranking of interdisciplinary projects scientific organizations, the growth of which is expressed in an increase in the share of the best alternatives.

The limiting point in the general case is the abscissa of the point of intersection of the line of growth and the line of decrease in the effectiveness of interdisciplinary projects of scientific organizations. The value of efficiency grows at those points of the x-axis, where the line of the next subordinate project crosses the growing line for the last time.

Proceeding from this and according to his understanding of the primary importance of the efficiency coefficients of scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects, the decision maker first selects the appropriate interval, and then within it determines his own optimal variant of the complex ranking of alternatives according to their estimates. The characteristic points of the efficiency curves of scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects are preliminarily found analytically. If, however, it is used to calculate the efficiency with arbitrary parameters of scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects, then the discrepancy between the graphs obtained by different principles of optimality can be quite noticeable [17, 18].

The hierarchical method for determining the parameters of the effectiveness of scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects is implemented

on the example of choosing the best digital technologies. Let the maximum values of supply and demand for digital solutions be chosen as the main indicators of scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects, and the investment and operating costs associated with this alternative as secondary indicators. Let also among the main ones, the indicator of demand is more priority, and both secondary indicators of digitalization are approximately equivalent.

To determine the efficiency ratings, we move to the second (lowest) level of the hierarchy, where we consider the supply indicator to be the main one, and the demand indicator to be the secondary one. After that, at the second level, we apply the above method of actions of the decision maker and, as a result, we obtain comprehensive assessments of the effectiveness of the main level. Of course, in the general case, it may be necessary to move to lower levels of the hierarchy, but there is always the opportunity to go to some lower level, where in each group of indicators there will be either only one indicator, or several equivalent ones, and therefore with the definition of complex assessments each group will have no problems.

After solving the problem at this level, it becomes defined and it is decided to pass a comprehensive assessment of scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects at the next highest level. So we are gradually moving up to the main level of scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects efficiency. Here are some properties of the model (in addition to those mentioned above):

- if, when comparing two alternatives of scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects, one dominates the other in all indicators, then its assessment of effectiveness is greater;

- if, when comparing two alternatives, one dominates the other in terms of digitalization parameters, then its efficiency rating is greater;

- with changes in the parameters of supply and demand (one of them or both) of a separate alternative, its assessment of efficiency changes in the same direction;

- if these parameters change proportionally for all alternatives, then all evaluations of the scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects effectiveness remain unchanged.

A significant effect, namely a twofold increase in productivity, is observed in different types of digital solutions [19, 20]. Similar results were obtained for wider groups of digital interdisciplinary projects, but, in general, these studies are unstructured and selective, and require further clarification and generalization, preferably experimentally confirmed. Since different scientific groups are active at different stages of the scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects implementation, the optimal nature of their performance may differ significantly, it is advisable to consider the possibility of establishing a dynamic mode of influencing managerial decision-making. The industrial application of the

proposed method of intensifying the process of selecting and implementing scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects could lead to a significant reduction in the cost of marketing research or even a complete rejection of them, and, consequently, increase efficiency, reduce the cost of digital technologies and, in the long term, bring both as separate enterprises and the state as a whole to scientific and technological independence.

One of the likely methods of influencing the actors of digital technologies is the use of science-based decision support algorithms. It has been established that individual actors are involved at different stages of the production of knowledge-intensive digital solutions, therefore it is advisable to study the possibility of using various types of impacts that are variable in time, which will probably be able to reduce dependence on foreign technologies and, therefore, significantly increase the overall efficiency of scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects.

The proposed mathematical model provides decision makers with the opportunity to choose new technologies or equipment for the modernization of digital production. Approximately, the volume of expenses for own needs for a specific digital production installation can be estimated from the technical and characteristics of the manufacturer of the specified equipment, presented in the documentation in order to clarify for a certain area the scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects effectiveness can be established by the method of computational experiment. From an economic point of view, the duration of the technological cycle for the implementation of digital technologies is important, which is the determining factor in the cost of production of high-tech products.

Multifactorial ranking of alternatives for scientific organizations interdisciplinary projects is considered as a problem of linear programming and is achieved by their comprehensive evaluation in terms of performance indicators.

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